

The Wilson effect: a new perspective using machine learning techniques in Python

2405239

April 15, 2021

Abstract

To demonstrate the Wilson effect, a SVM model will be trained and used with STARA. The geometry of a sunspot, which appeared on the solar surface on February 2014, will be studied by performing segmentations of its umbra and penumbra. When the sunspot approaches the East and West limbs, the relative widths between penumbrae become 1.50 ± 0.112 and 1.12 ± 0.0415 , respectively. This will evidence that there exist an East-West asymmetry, particularly stronger at $40^\circ < \theta < 80^\circ$. By modelling the depression of a sunspot as a cylinder, its depth will be broadly estimated to be 438 km at the East limb, whereas it will be overstated at the centre and West limb. The sunspot's appearance and depth at the West limb should be, therefore, further researched.

1 Introduction

Sunspots are cooler and visibly darker areas appearing temporarily on the solar surface. The Heliosismic and Magnetic Imager (HMI), aboard the Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO), has been providing us with solar images (4096x4096 pixels) to explore sunspots since 2010. However, some of their basic properties are still unknown. [1].

In the last two decades, automated solar-feature detection methods have been developed for the analysis of this data. The Sunspot Tracking and Recognition Algorithm (STARA) detects sunspots in optical continuum images by morphological image processing [2].

A complementary technique for the automatic classification of sunspots consists on employing a machine learning algorithm: Support Vector Machines (SVMs) [3]. To implement machine learning with SVM in Python, scikit-learn library is used. It includes a particular SVM classifier: Support Vector Classification (SVC) class, which can be used to perform a binary classification with a linear kernel. If the SVM learning is successful, it will be able to accurately predict on a testing set.

These techniques can be combined to study a particular characteristic of sunspots: the Wilson effect (1769). Geometrically, it is described by the factor f of Bray and

Loughhead (1958). The factor varies with heliocentric observing angle θ (see Appendix A, Figure 4). A East-West asymmetry was also observed between the two solar hemispheres. Several explanations exist but an agreement on this has not been reached.

The accepted explanation for the Wilson effect models sunspots as a depression in the solar surface. Values for this depression have been given by Wilson himself, Bray & Loughhead (1964), Gokhale & Zwaan (1972), Prokakis (1974) and other authors. However, an agreement on this has neither been reached. [4, 1, 5].

The aim of this project was to create a model that allowed for the automatic detection of sunspots to demonstrate the Wilson effect. In particular, the objective was to validate the East-West asymmetry of this effect, and to provide a broad estimate of the Wilson depression.

The first section of this report will cover background theory. The second section will cover the method followed by the results and discussion. These will be compared to previous work made by T.Prokakis, R.E. Loughhead and R.J. Bray.

2 Background Theory

STARA uses a nonlinear processing technique that involves two fundamental operations: erosion and dilation, and a probe called the structuring element. The image is produced by applying a top-hat transform. This a pixel-by-pixel subtraction of the original image with a new profile that has been morphologically eroded and dilated. The erosion and dilation operations are described in detail by F.T. Watson et al.[6].

On the other hand, SVMs can also help as a classification tool with the study of sunspots. SVMs find the largest separation between two classes, which are divided by the separating hyperplane [7]. SVM algorithm involves a kernel function, which adds a dimension to the data transforming it into the required form. In this experiment, a linear kernel is used since data can be separated by a single line [8]. To fit the model, the two inputs arrays needed are the X and y training arrays, with shape (number of samples, number of features), and (number of samples), respectively. The features are the characteristic properties of the samples used to train the model. Preprocessing the features allows to improve the performance of the model. This can involve standardization of the features so that the algorithm weighs them equally. After scaling the features, these are splitted into the training set and the test set. For imbalanced datasets, the low performance on the minority class can be improved by undersampling, which randomly deletes values in the majority class [9, 10, 11] . In Python, the library used for this method is the imbalanced-learn (imblearn) library. The SVM performance can be evaluated with the confusion matrix. It summarises the correct and incorrect predictions providing numbers for the four possible outcomes (see Figure 1). Other metrics derived from the confusion matrix are the accuracy, the precision and the recall.

One of the studied properties of sunspots is the Wilson effect. Visually, the appearance of a sunspot close to the limb shows an increase of the penumbra width

True Negative	False Negative	<i>No</i>	Predicted values
False Positive	True Positive	<i>Yes</i>	
		<i>No</i>	
		<i>Yes</i>	
Actual values			

Table 1: Structure for a 2x2 Confusion Matrix

towards the edge to that towards the centre [4]. This geometrical effect is quantified by f ,

$$f = \frac{AN}{A'N'}, \quad (1)$$

where f is the factor of Bray and Loughhead, and AN and $A'N'$ are the apparent widths of penumbrae, towards and away from the solar limb, respectively. These are measured along the greatest line of foreshortening going through the sunspot centroid [12] (see Appendix A, Figure 4).

According to Wilson, this phenomenon is due to the fact that radiation from sunspot umbra originates from a layer deeper than the photosphere. Values for this depression have been given fundamentally by studying the magnetic field of sunspots [13, 5], or by geometrical inspection [1].

3 Method

The sunspots data used for this experiment is from the HMI. The HMI files were loaded as maps using SunPy Python library, commonly used in solar physics. In particular, the 2D images converted into maps contain metadata (data about that particular map). The maps can be easily visualized.

Two series of data were used: weekly data from January 1, 2001 to December 27, 2014; and six hours apart data from February 9, 2014 to February 19, 2014. The first data set was employed for the SVM learning and validation of the model. The second data set was specifically chosen to study the Wilson effect.

3.1 SVM training and validation of model

The SunspotLab is a coding environment written by the demonstrator of this laboratory. It contains functions to evaluate regions from the solar maps and to perform operations on them. I used the `SunspotSelector` class from this .py file to select regions (128x128 pixels) on 20 maps. The selection was stored using the pickle library. The model was trained with the sunspots' most characteristic features in pixels. For example, the dimmer luminosity towards the edge of the solar disk was quantified by computing the change in pixel intensity as the distance from the centre increased (limb darkening). With the help of the demonstrator, I defined a function, `calculate_features`, which looped through the original number of chunks (32x32x20) and coordinates of the selected regions (for details on the function, see Appendix B).

These number of samples and features built the X training array. For the y array, I used `binary_mask` from `coords` function from SunspotLab script. For this step, I defined another function, `calculate_labels`, to loop through all the

maps (for details on the function, see Appendix B). `binary mask from coords` returned a 32x32 array for each image. For each chunk, the array contained a 0 or a 1 (for no sunspot and sunspot, respectively). Both the mask and the features were flattened so that the X training array and y training array became a 2D and 1D array, respectively (see Theory).

To train the model, I first scaled the features array. Secondly, I splitted the features and labels data set into training and testing arrays. Then, the training arrays were undersampled, which resulted on 33 samples on the minority class (with sunspot) and 15327 samples on the majority class (without sunspot). Afterwards, the SVM classifier was created. With the new class distribution, I fitted the model. Finally, the model was used to predict new values on a data set.

I performed the validation of the classifier's performance over 10 random files of the same HMI weekly data. I used the function `overplot spots from mask from SunspotLab` script to check whether the predicted labels by the model corresponded to the sunspots present on the images. To plot the mask, I reshaped it to get the original 32x32 array (see Appendix A, Figure 5).

3.2 The Wilson effect

From exploring HMI data in the browser, I identified a candidate to study the Wilson effect. I determined the factor f for different θ , following R.E. Loughhead and R.J Bray approach [14].

I started by defining a new function, `calculate regions`, to extract regions from the February maps (for details on the function, see Appendix B). This function used `scipy.ndimage.label` function to get an array where each sunspot predicted (in the binary mask) had a unique label. `calculate regions` returned also the number of sunspots. This array was needed to use `select regions` function from SunspotLab enviroment, as well as the number of sunspots. `select regions` was used in range from 1 (index 0 gave the corner coordinates of the whole plot), to the number of sunspots + 1 (so that all contiguous regions were plotted). `extracted regions` function from SunspotLab returned the SunPy map of a region given the particular corner coordinates.

Afterwards, I used STARA script provided to segmentate the umbra and penumbra of the sunspot on each on these regions (see Figure 1) . The structuring element used was a circle whose angular radius was changed according to the particular map. Other parameters specified were the median filter, which averaged features smaller than the size set, the threshold pixel intensity and the limb filter. Since I was interested on studying these features close to the limb, I set the limb filter to neglect features only within a 2% percentage of the radius of the disk. Most of the regions segmentated were predicted by the SVM classifier. However, for the frames where the sunspot was closer to the limb (February 9 and February 19), a cropped map was needed since these two regions were not returned by the model. The code to produce the cropped map was provided by the supervisor of the experiment. The arguments specified were the minimum and maximum helioprojective longitude and latitude in arc seconds, using the SkyCoord class from Astropy.coordinates package.

Furthermore, I used `get_regions` function, from STARA script, on each umbra segmentation. The function returned the coordinates of the centroid.

3.2.1 Estimating f and θ

STARA segmentation of umbra and penumbra returned an array of False and True elements for each coordinate of the region outside and inside of the area segmented, respectively. I flattened the middle row (known from its shape) to build a mask with the 1D indices of the True elements. The middle row would correspond to the line closest to the centroid (see Appendix A, Figure 4). I repeated this procedure with the penumbra segmentation. With the two masks, the two apparent widths of the penumbra, towards the centre and towards the limb, were estimated. I subtracted the penumbra's mask first entry with umbra's mask last entry, and vice versa. The ratio of the two would return the f factor. Assuming that the Sun rotates on its axis once in 25 days, I estimated θ from $\theta = 0^\circ$ frame (February 14) (see Table 3).

The errors on f and θ on Table 3 were estimated using error propagation formulae [15]. As discussed by F.T. Watson et al., STARA algorithm determined the perimeter of the region with an uncertainty of ± 1 pixel [16]. Taking this error on the mask subtraction between umbra and penumbra entries, led to the quoted error (see Appendix C). Regarding θ , the error was calculated by taking the difference with the true θ , which varied with φ . I used the coefficients estimated by H. Snodgrass and R.Ulrich to define the function `error_theta` depending on φ and on the days passed since $\theta = 0^\circ$ frame [17] (for details on the function, see Appendix B). Since February 14th frame was the 0th frame (days = 0), no errors are shown in Table 3 for $\theta = 0^\circ$. Values of f and θ , with errors, were plotted aiming to reproduce the East-West asymmetry also demonstrated by T.Prokakis [?] (see Figure 2).

3.2.2 Estimating the depth of the sunspot

I estimated the depth of the sunspot using the cylinder depression model described by F.T. Watson et al. [6]. From this model, the decrease in apparent diameter of the sunspot changes with observing angle θ ,

$$l_{\text{app}} = l - h \times \tan\theta \quad (2)$$

where l_{app} is the apparent diameter of the sunspot, l is the true diameter (at $\theta = 0^\circ$) and h is the height of the cylinder (the depression).

For different l_{app} and θ values, l and h could be estimated from a system of linear equations (see Table 4). The error was calculated using error propagation formulae on (2) rearranged for h (see Appendix C). Note that $l = l_{\text{app}}$ at $\theta = 0^\circ$.

I determined l_{app} from `get_distance_from_centroid` function, which looped through the pixel coordinates inside the segmentation. I calculated the distance (in pixels) as the modulus of the vector joining the centroid and each of these coordinates. Then, I took the maximum of these distances values. I converted this distance in arc seconds using World Coordinate System keywords (Astropy) conversion of pixels to degrees. This would return the umbra apparent radius. Hence, I multiplied by 2. Finally, I converted the helioprojective arc seconds distance into meters using the angular diameter formula (with $1 \text{ au} \gg l_{\text{app}}$).

I determined the error on l_{app} by assuming an uncertainty of ± 1 pixel on the contour coordinate [6]. This coordinate yielded the maximum distance to the centroid. Then, I used error propagation formulae, for which I defined a new function, `error_lapp`, to perform these calculations (for details on the function, see Appendix B).

4 Results and discussion

5103	1	<i>No</i>	Predicted values
2	14	<i>Yes</i>	
<i>No</i>	<i>Yes</i>		
Actual values			

Table 2: Confusion Matrix displaying the performance of the SVM classifier. The metrics derived have values: precision = 0.93, recall = 0.875, accuracy = 0.99.

Figure 1: Umbra (purple) and penumbra (red) segmentations of extracted solar map regions. The first row show the sunspot at the East limb (from February 9 to February 11), whereas the sunspot is approaching the West limb on images from second row (February 17 to February 19). Note that the segmentations at the centre are not included since they did not display any relevant features ($f \approx 1$).

The main limitations found in the model were the dependence of its performance with the chosen features and the random state argument, as well as the drawbacks from undersampling. The precision of the model was quite sensitive to the chosen

East limb

Date	9 Feb	10 Feb	11 Feb
$\theta(^{\circ})$	79.2 ± 1.67	61.2 ± 1.30	43.2 ± 0.92
Dapp (m)	$2.7 \cdot 10^7 \pm 1.05 \cdot 10^7$	$2.55 \cdot 10^7 \pm 9.92 \cdot 10^6$	$5.47 \cdot 10^7 \pm 2.13 \cdot 10^7$
f	1.5 ± 0.112	1.31 ± 0.337	1.27 ± 0.0262

Centre

Date	13 Feb	14 Feb	15 Feb
$\theta(^{\circ})$	14.4 ± 0.31	0	14.4 ± 0.62
Dapp (m)	$1.54 \cdot 10^8 \pm 6.38 \cdot 10^7$	$1.29 \cdot 10^8 \pm 5.02 \cdot 10^7$	$1.18 \cdot 10^8 \pm 4.58 \cdot 10^7$
f	1.21 ± 0.019	1.01 ± 0.089	1.14 ± 0.014

West limb

Date	17 Feb	18 Feb	19 Feb
$\theta(^{\circ})$	43.2 ± 0.92	50.4 ± 1.07	72.3 ± 1.52
Dapp (m)	$8.27 \cdot 10^7 \pm 3.44 \cdot 10^7$	$7.27 \cdot 10^7 \pm 3.03 \cdot 10^7$	$3.40 \cdot 10^7 \pm 1.32 \cdot 10^7$
f	1.06 ± 0.0145	1.13 ± 0.0227	1.12 ± 0.0415

Table 3: Estimates of l_{app} and f with errors for the sunspot tracked across the solar disk from February 9, 2014 to February 19, 2014. θ is the heliocentric angle changing with its passage from East to West limb. Note that AN measured from February 9 to 13 (towards East) is $A'N'$ from February 15 to 19 (towards West), such that $f > 1$.

random state argument, which should not vary the algorithm’s performance. This number should have been chosen in the first place as a constant. In addition, the undersampling could have removed a crucial sample from the majority class. For instance, a visibly dark sunspot at the West limb. This is important particularly for studying the geometry of the sunspots as they approach the limb. However, as being discussed by B. Juba S.L. Hai, correcting for the imbalance on the training data set via this technique or other is critical [18]. Regarding the features chosen for training the model, the mode as well as the distance-from-origin feature improved the metrics. On the other hand, the imbalanced training data led naturally to a high accuracy, since the model found it easier to predict correctly most of the time the majority class. Therefore precision and recall became critical [18]. Table 2 indicates the model low outcome of FN (1), and FP (2), which agrees with the high precision and recall values returned by the system. In general, the SVM prediction results were very encouraging, as well as the validation (see Appendix A, Figure 5). The three metrics computed were high, meaning that the many results returned by the model were labelled correctly.

The fact that sunspots for more than 70 solar maps (training, validation and

Figure 2: Factor f as a function of heliocentric angle θ .

East limb	Centre	West limb
$4.38 \cdot 10^5 \pm 2.05 \cdot 10^5$	$2.66 \cdot 10^7 \pm 5.2 \cdot 10^7$	$9.70 \cdot 10^6 \pm 2.6 \cdot 10^7$

Table 4: Best estimates of h in meters at the East limb, at the centre and at the West limb. They were calculated using pairs of l_{app} and θ from February 9 and 10, February 13 and 15, and February 17 and 19, respectively.

Wilson effect) needed to be detected, proves the importance of automatising the process by using STARA, for instance. However, this algorithm is not perfect. Some subtle problems include the lost of accuracy as a sunspot approaches the limb. This is caused by the geometrical-foreshortening effects (as seen in Figure 1, and Figure 4 in Appendix) [2]. This did not only depend on the algorithm, but also on the training of the model to deal with limb darkening, though the change on the sunspot's shape is independent and could not be controlled by neither STARA nor the SVM. In fact, this led to the fundamental result shown in Table 3: measurements became both more complicated and uncertain towards the solar limb. This fact has limited the experiment in different ways. For example, regions containing the sunspot closer to the limb were not predicted by the model and required a cropped map.

Regarding the results for f , Table 3 shows that the ratio of the penumbrae widths is closest to unity by February 14, as expected. Starting from the East limb, the Wilson effect is demonstrated, with the penumbra width closer to the edge being at most 1.5 of that nearer the centre. Interestingly, R.E. Loughhead and R.J. Bray

found that their closest measurement to the East limb revealed $f = 2$. At $\theta \approx 44^\circ$, we both estimated $f \approx 1.2$. However, their estimates showed $f < 1$ whereas mines did not, though I did not evaluate a frame where the sunspot was observed at $\theta \approx 8^\circ$. Regarding the West limb measurements, they bore a close resemblance to those proposed by these authors. However, my analysis did not reveal such a large f at the West limb. This could be attributed to the fact that the shape of my sunspot near the West limb became very distorted. This led to a very awkward segmentation (recall Figure 1) and therefore, to an uncertain umbra and penumbra masks to calculate the relative penumbral widths. Apart from this slight discordance, the result is a confirmation of both the Wilson effect and of the East-West asymmetry. R.J. Bray and R.E. Loughhead hypothesized about the Wilson effect being less marked at the East limb due to the sunspot being measured along lines differing by $\theta \approx 7^\circ$. This argument is very plausible, since I noted that the middle row of the umbra and segmentation array did not provide the expected f . Therefore, I modified the index of the row, which would correspond to the angle with respect to the horizontal on R.E. Loughhead and R.J. Bray's analysis. Hence, extreme caution must be taken when establishing the line along which the width will be measured. These authors concluded that the East limb measurements were the accurate ones, which, importantly, matched my estimates for the f at the East limb. The discrepancies found are likely due to the small scale of the quantity being measured, as well as on the differences between the methods. The errors were also estimated in a different way. Nevertheless, the uncertainties that I quoted are in line with previous work, differing at most by 30%.

When comparing their method to the one described in this report, using an automated tool for tracing the outline of the sunspots is clearly less cumbersome. STARA algorithm segmentation is a more elegant way of demonstrating the Wilson effect compared to manual work, where irregularities and projections are likely to be neglected.

In contrast, T. Prokakis method of demonstrating this asymmetry seems to be well-founded and more practical than R.E. Loughhead and R.J. Bray's [12]. Figure 2 is, in fact, reminiscent of the results found by T. Prokakis, where the asymmetry began to be visible at $\theta \approx 15^\circ$. This was approximately in agreement with what I found for the frames close to the central meridian. However, further data collection is required with frames at $\theta < 14^\circ$ so that the lower limit of the asymmetry can be compared. Furthermore, this study reinforced the author's observation that the asymmetry got stronger at $40^\circ < \theta < 80^\circ$, although my results for the upper limit of f at the West limit differ slightly. This finding was anticipated by the fact that the sunspot could not be tracked further than February 19.

Regarding h results, the unexpected values that I found using the geometric model from F.T Watson et al. were overestimated and poor. The errors were very large as well, supporting the fact that h estimates were too high and inconsistent. There are several sources of unreliability in the method used. For instance, the calculation of l_{app} strongly depended on the segmentation. However, the foremost cause was the dependence with θ . As shown in Table 4, the unique satisfactory agreement with estimates from F.T Watson et al. was found at the East limb [6]. I was surprised to find that h became so overstated as the sunspot moved across the solar disk towards the West limb. These values revealed that, even though F.T. Watson's model was

appropriate to investigate the sunspot visibility and appearance, it was too simple to be considered alone for an estimation of h . R.E. Loughhead and R.J. Bray claimed that the depression of the sunspot varied with θ . My findings were in agreement with this idea, also supported by T. Prokakis and V.F. Chistyakov. However, they contradicted V.F. Chistyakov's second conclusion about h decreasing towards the West limb [19]. Clearly, future work needs to be carried out to establish how the Wilson depression can be accurately determined geometrically.

4.1 Conclusion

The SVM classifier together with STARA have allowed me to investigate geometrically the Wilson effect in a more practical way compared to the techniques used to this day. The results for the East-West asymmetry and for h confirmed previous evidence of the limitations of detecting sunspots at high longitude using an automated algorithm. There was an exceptional agreement between the results found for f at the East limb and that determined by R.E. Loughhead and R.J. Bray, as well as T. Prokakis. The Wilson effect and the East-West asymmetry was clearly demonstrated. There was also a satisfactory agreement between the calculated h with that estimated by F.T. Watson et al. at the East Limb. However, this study failed to obtain an accurate estimate, fundamentally of h , at the West limb. These findings show that the West limb poses intriguing questions on the appearance of sunspots and its depth.

This work had led me to conclude that the Wilson depression can not be understood as a sunspot's parameter to quantify alone, and that it might have a correlation with the East-West asymmetry. One potential application of this project could be determining h and f from a more complete geometrical and radiative transfer model of a sunspot, whose umbra and penumbra can be tracked at the West limb.

References

- [1] Solanki S K 2003 *The Astronomy and Astrophysics Review* **11** 153–286
- [2] Verbeeck C, Higgins P A, Colak T, Watson F T, Delouille V, Mampaey B and Qahwaji R 2013 *Solar Physics* **283** 67–95
- [3] Noble W S 2006 *Nature biotechnology* **24** 1565–1567
- [4] Chistyakov V 1962 *Soviet Astronomy* **5** 471
- [5] Löptien B, Lagg A, van Noort M and Solanki S K 2018 *Astronomy & Astrophysics* **619** A42
- [6] Watson F, Fletcher L, Dalla S and Marshall S 2009 *Solar Physics* **260** 5–19
- [7] Haroon D 2017 *Python Machine Learning Case Studies* (Springer)
- [8] Hertzmann A and Fleet D 2010 *Computer Science Department, University of Toronto*
- [9] Farquad M and Bose I 2012 *Decision Support Systems* **53** 226–233

- [10] Akbani R, Kwek S and Japkowicz N 2004 Applying support vector machines to imbalanced datasets *European conference on machine learning* (Springer) pp 39–50
- [11] Palade V 2013 *Imbalanced Learning: Foundations, Algorithms, and Applications*; Wiley: Hoboken, NJ, USA 83
- [12] Prokakis T 1974 *Solar Physics* **35** 105–110
- [13] Solanki S, Rüedi I and Livingston W 1992 *Astronomy and Astrophysics* **263** 312–322
- [14] Loughhead R and Bray R 1958 *Australian Journal of Physics* **11** 177–184
- [15] University H 2007 *A Summary of Error Propagation* (Harvard University)
- [16] Watson F T, Fletcher L and Marshall S 2011 *Astronomy & Astrophysics* **533** A14
- [17] Snodgrass H B and Ulrich R K 1990 *The Astrophysical Journal* **351** 309–316
- [18] Juba B and Le H S 2019 Precision-recall versus accuracy and the role of large data sets *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence* vol 33 pp 4039–4048
- [19] Chistyakov V 1962 *Soviet Astronomy* **6** 363

Statement of work

Since this project was a computational one, based on a lot of unseen Python functions and packages, the speed at which I wrote the code during the first couple of weeks was much slower compared to that during the rest of the sessions.

The code for selecting the chunks on the solar maps to train the model, as discussed throughout the report, was provided by the demonstrator via the SunspotLab python script. This included the SunspotSelector class, the function to overplot the mask predicted by the SVM as well as the select regions and get info on regions function. The STARA python script and the code to produce a cropped map was given as well by the demonstrator.

This first part of the project was more collaborative than the second one. Even though I progressed individually during the lab sessions, I frequently asked questions to the demonstrator about the code. Student A and Student B also helped me to understand, for instance, how to use the pickle library, and how to define the initial functions that would allow for the training of the model.

However, the second part of the project was completely individual. I realised that the first part had helped me to feel confident on defining new functions, making plots and writing loops without external help, though I did ask the demonstrator any time I had questions. I did a lot of background reading regarding the research done on the Wilson effect. That allowed me to define the aim of my project, which I then discussed with the demonstrator. Then, I got the idea of using the approach from R.E. Loughhead and R.J. Bray of determining f via my own method, as well as of taking the model from F.T. Watson et al. to estimate h . I invested a lot of time on thinking on how to make these estimates (via linear system of equation, or I could have also considered the visible area of the sunspot to do the calculation...). The results from this part were supervised by the demonstrator, who orientated me on the limitations of the method and the results found. Furthermore, I helped Student C with the method that could be used to study the geometry of the sunspot (via segmentation and calculation of distance from centroid).

At the end of the project, I realised how much my Python programming skills had improved by tackling coding problems both in and out of laboratory time. Since I performed a lot of literature research, I also learnt how to distinguish the fundamental results from other authors as well as the limitations and benefits from their method compared to mine.

Appendix

A.1 Models

This appendix contains the two models from which f and h were inferred, as well as the validation of the SVM classifier.

Figure 3: Figure taken from F.T. Watson et al. showing the model for a sunspot profile. The left is a profile view of the sunspot, where θ is the heliocentric angle and $d - l$ is the apparent sunspot diameter, l_{app} . The right image corresponds to the view when looking down to the sunspot along the normal. Note that the shaded area is the visible area of the spot due to the walls obscuring the base l .

Figure 4: Figure taken from R.E. Loughhead and R.J. Bray. AN and $A'N'$ are the apparent widths of the penumbra on the outer and inner side respectively, as the sunspot approaches the solar limb.

Figure 5: Model’s predicted mask onto original November 23, 2013, solar map. The selected regions are drawn in red.

B.2 Code

- Function to calculate the features of the selected sunspots, for the training of the model.

```
def calculate_features(sfiles, boxSize):
    mean, std, _min, _max, _iqr, dist, mode = [], [], [],
        [], [], [], []

    for a, file in tqdm(enumerate(sfiles)):
        mappy = Map(file)
        mappy.data[np.isnan(mappy.data)] = 0
        for j in range(32):
            for i in range(32):
                chunk_map = mappy.data[j*boxSize:(j+1)*
                    boxSize, i*boxSize:(i+1)*boxSize]
                #print(chunk_map.shape)
                mean.append(np.mean(chunk_map))

                #feature 1 : average intensity
                std.append(np.std(chunk_map))

                #feature 2 : standard deviation
                _min.append(np.min(chunk_map))
```

```

        #feature 3 : minimum intensity
        _max.append(np.max(chunk_map))

        #feature 4 : maximum intensity
        _iqr.append(stats.iqr(chunk_map))

        #feature 5 : inter-quartile range
        dist.append(np.sqrt((16-i)**2 + (16-j)
            **2))

        #feature 6 : radial distance for limb
        darkening
        mode.append(statistics.mode(chunk_map.
            flatten()))

#mode = np.array(mode)
#Normalize the radial distance:
norm_dist = np.array(dist)/np.max(dist)
features2 = np.column_stack(((mean, std, _min, _max,
    _iqr, norm_dist, mode)))
return features2

```

- Function to get the labels for each chunk (0 or 1).

```

def calculate_labels(sfiles, BoxCoords):
    labels_ = []
    for a, file in tqdm(enumerate(sfiles)):
        mappy = Map(file)
        mappy.data[np.isnan(mappy.data)] = 0
        y_labels = binary_mask_from_coords(BoxCoords[a],
            mappy, boxSize=boxSize).flatten() #flattening
            to obtain a list
        labels_.append(y_labels)
    labels2 = np.concatenate(labels_)
    return labels2

```

- Function to extract regions containing sunspots predicted by the model.

```

def calculate_regions(files_):

    feat_files = calculate_features(files_, boxSize) #put
        this inside the loop
    sc_feat_files = scaler.transform(feat_files)
    prediction_files = clf2.predict(sc_feat_files)
    ext_regions = []

```

```

for index, file in enumerate(files_):
    reg_smap = Map(file)

    #Reshape predictions into a binary mask:
    impred_files = prediction_files[index*1024:(index
+1)*1024].reshape(32,32) #1024 because is for
    a single image

    #Get labels for each unique feature, get the
    number of features(sunspots):
    labels_arr, idx = sp.ndimage.label(impred_files)

    regions_files = [] # one per image
    local_regions = [] # to store the regions of one
    image

    for i in range(1, idx+1):
        regions_files.append(select_region(labels_arr
, idx = i, boxSize = 128))
        #Array for the extracted regions:
    print(regions_files)
        #Iterate over each selected region to create
        submaps (and plot them afterwards)
    for a in range(len(regions_files)): #if we want
        to use an index, use range()

        #Get the regions for each image individually:
        local_regions.append(extract_region(reg_smap,
            regions_files[a][0], regions_files[a][1])
        )

    ext_regions.append(local_regions) #list of the
    regions for each image
        #this ext_regions are submaps
return ext_regions

```

- Function to calculate the distance in m from the centroid (x0, y0) to the maximum pixel coordinate within the area described by the segmentation.

```

def get_distance_from_centroid(x0, y0, segmentation):

    #Empty arrays:
    points = []
    lengths = []
    x_coordseg = []
    y_coordseg = []

    #Get x and y coordinated of the segmentation:

```

```

points = np.argwhere(seg01)

seg_x = points[:, 1] #Indices for the x coordinates
      in segmentation
seg_y = points[:, 0] #Indices for the y coordinates
      in segmentation

#Loop through x and y coordinates in segmentation
points:
for i in range(len(seg_y)):
    x = seg_x[i] #Index them, if not we will be
      taking the whole list
    y = seg_y[i] #same

    #Array with all x and y coordinates indices from
      segmentation:
    x_coordseg.append(x)
    y_coordseg.append(y)
    #print(np.max(x_coordseg[0]))
    # print(np.max(y_coordseg[0]))

    #Length of the vector joining x0 and the
      segmentation point:
    length = np.sqrt(((x-x0)**2) + ((y-y0)**2))

    #Set nan values in length array to 0:
    #length[np.isnan(length)] = 0

    lengths.append(length) #inside the loop because
      if not we are goint to get just the last one
    # lengths[np.isnan(lengths)] = 0

#loc = np.argmax(lengths)
#print(np.max(lengths))
#Get the maximum distance and convert in arc sec: (
  lapp)
dist = ((np.max(lengths))*0.00014008*3600)

#Get dist in m with angula diameter formula (recall
  the assumptions):
#dist in arc sec would approximate to the radius
#Multiply by two to get the total length
#Conversion of arc sec into radians using the angular
  diameter formula:
lapp = (dist*2)*au.value/(3600*180/np.pi)

```

```

#Get lapp: apparent diameter of the sunspot:

return x_coordseg, y_coordseg, lengths, lapp

```

- Function to calculate the error on the apparent diameter of the sunspot:

```

def error_lapp(x_coordseg, y_coordseg, lengths):

#Find index of maximum in distance array – length:
imax = np.argmax(lengths)

#Use the index to find x_max and y_max coordinate in
pixel:
x_max = x_coordseg[imax]
y_max = y_coordseg[imax]

#Assuming no significant centroid error:
#sigma x_max = sigma X = 1 px
#sigma y_max = sigma Y = 1 px

#Error on X squared and Y squared:
sigma_X2 = (x_max**2)*2*(1/x_max)
sigma_Y2 = (y_max**2)*2*(1/y_max)

#Error on Q = X^2 + Y^2:
sigma_Q = np.sqrt((sigma_X2)**2 + (sigma_Y2)**2)
Q = sigma_X2 + sigma_Y2

#Error on maximum length in px:
sigma_l = np.max(lengths)*(1/2)*(sigma_Q/Q)

#Error on maximum length in arc sec:
A = 0.0001408*3600 #constant for conversion
sigma_larcsec = A*sigma_l

#Error on maximum length in meters – dapp:
B = 2*au.value/206265
sigma_lapp = B*sigma_larcsec

return sigma_lapp

```

- Function to calculate the error on the heliocentric angle θ .

```

def error_theta(latitude, days):

#Define coefficients from Solar Surface Rotation Eq (
paper –T):

```

```

#Assume they have no error:
#units = microrad/s
A_ = 2.972
B_ = -0.484
C_ = -0.361

#Convert them into deg/rad:
A = (A_*(10**(-6))*180*24*3600)/(np.pi)
B = (B_*(10**(-6))*180*24*3600)/(np.pi)
C = (C_*(10**(-6))*180*24*3600)/(np.pi)

#Define equation:
#w: angular velocity in degrees per day
#latitude in degrees
w = A + B*((np.sin(latitude))**2) + C*((np.sin(
    latitude))**4)

#Calculate difference with assumed w:
w_used = 360/25 # degrees/day
sigma_w = w - w_used #w_used is less because we
    assumed sunspot at equator

#Theta = days(from theta = 0) x w_used
#days have no error - calculated from frame
    differences

#Multiplication error propagation formula:
sigma_theta = days*sigma_w

return sigma_theta

```

C.3 Error propagation

- Error calculation of umbra and penumbra masks used to determine f :

Let $P = p[-1] - u[0]$, for penumbra and umbra masks p and u , respectively. Note that index -1 corresponds to the last element and index 0 to the first element. Also, let $Q = u[-1] - p[0]$.

If $f = P / Q$ (recall 1), then

$$\sigma_f = f \times \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_P}{P}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_Q}{Q}\right)^2} \quad (3)$$

- Error calculation on h :

Let $\Delta l = l - l_{\text{app}}$. Then,

$$\sigma_h = h \times \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_{\Delta l}}{\Delta l}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{\tan\theta}}{\tan\theta}\right)^2} \quad (4)$$

where $\sigma_{tan\theta}$ was calculated using a calculus approximation (partial differentiation), as follows:

$$\sigma_{tan\theta} = \sec^2\theta \times \sigma_{theta} \quad (5)$$

Also,

$$\sigma_{\Delta l} = \sqrt{(\sigma_l)^2 + (\sigma_{l_{app}})^2} \quad (6)$$

where $\sigma_{l_{app}}$ corresponds to the error on the apparent diameter of the sunspot on February 14.